

THE EFFECT OF MATRIX TOUGHNESS ON TENSILE AND COMPRESSIVE
BEHAVIORS FOR MONOFIBRE AND HYBRID FIBRE CROSS-PLIED
LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of matrix toughness on tensile and compressive behaviors of glass or/and carbon fibre reinforced cross-plyed laminate is presented. The results show that the tensile strength of laminates with the matrix toughness and the tensile strength, elongation and compressive strength when 0° layers are placed on the outside of laminates are larger than those when 90° layers are. As 90° layers replaced with hybrid ones in the toughened matrix, the tensile strength and elongation will increase. The matrix toughness can decrease slightly the compressive behaviors in the mono-fibre cross-plyed laminates. But the compressive strength increases when 90° layers replaced with hybrid ones.

INTRODUCTION

The cross-plyed laminate is one of the fundamental type of composites. It is very important to study its damage, failure process and theory for designing and applying the composite structures. A lot of works on them have been investigated [1-6]. The results show that the microcracks in 90° layers of cross-plyed composites under tension are initiated i.e. the matrix crack, interfacial debonding etc are occurred. The damage accumulation will decrease the tensile modulus, and the knee point will exhibit on the stress-strain curve. With the damage accumulation and propagation in 90° layers, the laminate occurs the delamination longitudinal crack and fibre fracture in 0° ones. At last, the composite will fracture.

Some people [7-9] intended to use the toughened matrix to increase the resistance to the crack initiation and propagation, the transverse tensile strength and failure strain of unidirectional composites, and to improve the resistance to damage and the strength of the crossplyed laminates. The others [5] sought the possibility that the hybridization would increase their mechanical behaviors. But the compressive properties and affecting factors are limited [4,6]. In the paper, we will study the effect of matrix toughness on tensile and compressive behaviors of the mono- and hybrid cross-plyed composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two epoxy systems (A and B) are used. Their cast mechanical properties are given in Table 1. High strength glass fiber (G F) and T-300 carbon fibre (C F) are the reinforcement.

In glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP) and carbon fibre reinforced

plastics (CFRP), their crossplied laminates, $[0_2/90_2]_s$ and $[90_2/0_2]_s$ are tested. But in carbon/glass hybrid composites (HFRP), $[0_2^G/90_2^C]_s$, $[90_2^C/0_2^G]_s$, $[0_2^C/90_2^G]_s$ and $[90_2^G/0_2^C]_s$ are used. Where the topnote C and G represent carbon and glass fibre reinforced unidirectional layers respectively. The volume ratio of carbon fibre and glass fibre HFRP is 0.45:0.48. The composites are cured in the cycle of 80 C°/2hr+120 C°/4hr and the pressure of 0.8Mpa. The crossplied laminate is about 1mm thick.

Table 1 The cast mechanical data

Epoxy System		A	B
Tensile Strength	Mpa	47.0	61.9
Tensile Modulus	Gpa	3.11	2.43
Tensile Failure Strain	0/0	1.51	8.22
Tensile Failure Energy	MJ/m ³	0.353	4.46
Impact Strength	KJ/m ²	8.65	20.8
Tensile Poisson's Ratio		0.30	0.31
Compressive Strength	Mpa	108	88.6
Compressive Modulus	Gpa	2.68	2.36
Compressive Proportional Strain	0/0	1.63	2.18
Compressive Failure Strain	0/0	8.13	13.0
Compressive Poisson's Ratio		0.33	0.37

In the crossplied laminates, the specimen size is 230 x 12.5 x 1mm. The compressive properties are tested by means of wedge-shaped fixture. The compressive specimen size of the unidirectional composites is 110 x 12.5 x 2mm with the gage length of 20mm, and 110 x 12.5 x 1mm of the crossplied laminates with the gage length of 14mm. The numbers of effective specimen are more than five.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

1. The Effect of Matrix Toughness on the properties of Unidirectional Composites Under Uniaxial Tension and Compression
Table 2 shows that their longitudinal tensile properties depend mainly on the fibre. But the matrix has a smaller effect on them.

The increasing of matrix toughness will increase the tensile strength and modulus slightly. Under longitudinal compression, however, its effect is shown to be different. The reason is that the fibre must be supported by the matrix. We conclude that the longitudinal compressive behaviors connect not only with the fibre, but also with the matrix. The effect of the fibre modulus on the compressive modulus of unidirectional composites is similar to the longitudinal tensile one, but the toughened matrix will increase it. The carbon fibre composite A and B (CFRP-A and CFRP-B) display the linear stress-strain behavior (Fig.1). The failure feature is the carbon fibre fractures at first and the specimen appears as the transverse cleavage crack or delamination under compression. But the stress-strain curve of GFRP is quite different from that of CFRP. They also display the linear nature at the initial stage, the nonlinear characteristics is followed. Their fracture morphology is shown in Fig.2 CFRP-A exhibits the transverse cleavage crack, fibre and matrix compressive failure. But GFRP-B occurs kinking, fibre shear crippling. The kinking band is seen on the specimen. Its formation is due to the matrix yielding or flowing. In C/G hybrid composites (HFRP) under compression. CFRP ply will prevent glass fibre from the previous buckling, and increase the composite stiffness, that is, the compressive stability of composites is enhanced, and GFRP ply can modify the toughness and suppress the rapid propagation of cracks, therefore the failure feature and compressive performance lie between CFRP and GFRP.

Table 2 Tensile and compressive data of the unidirectional composites

composite			GFRP		C/G RP		CFRP	
Epoxy System			A	B	A	B	A	B
Tensile Strength	Mpa	0	1400	1460	1040	1190	1110	1180
		90	24.4	30.8	26.2	33.7	27.7	34.8
Tensile Modulus	Gpa	0	49.7	56.6	88.7	95.9	114	125
		90	12.3	9.19	7.14	5.76	6.17	4.32
Tensile Failure Elongation 0/0		0	2.83	2.53	1.20	1.26	1.07	1.02
		90	0.29	0.40	0.31	0.61	0.68	0.84
Compressive Strength	Mpa	0	759	758	842	631	850	887
		90	154	137	142	118	122	107
Compressive Modulus	Gpa	0	53.1	50.0	87.0	68.2	140	130
		90	13.1	10.6	9.87	9.17	9.70	7.73
Compressive Failure Strain 0/0		0	1.70	1.90	0.97	1.00	0.61	0.68
		90	1.30	1.40	1.50	1.40	1.35	1.50
Fibre Volume Ratio	0/0	0	58.0	60.0	62.5	59.0	57.0	58.8
		90	58.0	61.0	62.5	61.7	57.0	58.8

Fig.1 Longitudinal compressive stress-strain curves of composites

a) GFRP-A b) GFRP-B

Fig.2 Photographs illustrating the compressive failure feature of GFRP

The matrix will have an effect on the transverse tensile behaviors of composites. The transverse tensile strength depends mainly on the matrix and interfacial strength, but the modulus and failure elongation have a close relationship with the transverse behaviors of the fibre. Because the transverse tensile modulus of carbon fibre is smaller than that of glass fibre, the transverse tensile modulus of GFRP is smaller than that of CFRP, too. The failure elongation, however, is reversed. After the matrix is toughened, the transverse tensile strength and failure strain will increase appreciably, but the modulus will decrease sharply. The transverse compressive strength and modulus of composites are larger than that of matrix, the failure strain is much smaller than that of matrix and close to that of fibre. They show that the matrix and fibre all affect the transverse compressive performance of composites. Their transverse compressive strength and modulus will increase with the matrix modulus.

2. The Effect of Matrix Toughness on the Tensile Properties of Crossplied Laminates.

In the crossplied laminates of two system, their stress-strain curves are given in Fig.3. Previously we have discussed their tensile behaviors in the brittle matrix composites, and analysed the reason that in composite A the tensile strength and elongation of 90° layers put on the outside are larger than those of 0° ones [5]. When the toughened matrix is used, the above conclusion is reversed (seen in Fig.3) i.e. the tensile strength and elongation when 0° layers are placed on the outside are larger than those when 90° ones are put on it. We consider that the matrix crack, debonding initiation and crack propagation in the transverse and longitudinal plies in the toughened crossplied laminates decrease so that the 0° ply can share more load and the whole of materials is enhanced. From the data, it is proved again that the strength of crossplied laminates with the toughened matrix is larger than that with the brittle matrix.

It is well known that the 0° ply (that is the reference ply) shares the majority of load in composites. When the 0° layers are glass fibre in the crossplied laminates of the brittle matrix, the tensile strength and elongation of $[0_2/90_2]_s$ are larger than that of $[0_2/90_2]_s$, that is, when 90° layers are replaced with hybrid ones, the tensile properties will increase. But as 0° layers are carbon fibre, the tensile behaviors decrease. In the toughened matrix, the 90° hybrid layers will increase the tensile strength and elongation of the crossplied composites no matter what the 0° ones are glass fibre or carbon fibre.

3. The Effect of Matrix Toughness on the Compressive Properties of Crossplied Composites

The compressive behaviors of the crossplied laminates are shown in Table 3 and 4. Reference [6] described the compressive behaviors of the thin crossplied composites. In the mono-or hybrid laminates, the buckling of the 0° layer, shear failure of the 90° one and a lot of delamination between the 0° and 90° layer are the failure feature when 0° plies are glass fibre. But when the 0° layers is replaced by carbon fibre, the 0° plies fracture. The matrix toughness has a little effect on the failure mode.

Table 3 and 4 shows that the compressive strength with outside 0° layers is bigger than with outside 90° ones in the laminates and the latter compressive behaviors of 90° glass layer laminates are larger than 90° carbon layers ones. The compressive strength and modulus of the 0° carbon fibre laminates are larger than that of the 0° glass fibre ones. For the hybrid crossplied laminates, the compressive strength of $[0_2^C/90_2^G]_s$ is the highest, but that of $[90_2^C/0_2^G]_s$ is the lowest. The compressive behaviors decrease slightly for the mono-fibre cross-plyed composites with outside 0° layers by the matrix toughness. But matrix toughness can increase the compressive strength of the cross laminates with outside 90° layer. For the HFRP. After the matrix is toughened. The compressive behaviors increase. Aside from the cross-plyed HFRP with outside 90° layers, their modulus is decrease.

CONCLUSION

1. In the unidirectional composites the matrix toughness has a little effect on the longitudinal tensile properties. Only the longitudinal strength and modulus increase slightly. The increasing of matrix toughness will decrease the longitudinal compressive modulus and increase the longitudinal compressive failure strain and change the compressive failure mode of the composite.

Table 3 The compressive behaviors of the mono-fibre cross-laminates

		A				B			
		GFRP		CFRP		GFRP		CFRP	
		$[0_2/90_2]_s$	$[90_2/0_2]_s$	$[0_2/90_2]_s$	$[90_2/0_2]_s$	$[0_2/90_2]_s$	$[90_2/0_2]_s$	$[0_2/90_2]_s$	$[90_2/0_2]_s$
Compressive Strength	Mpa	265	119	239	158	482	186	457	162
Compressive Modulus	Gpa	44.4	43.4	40.8	38.9	76.4	70.3	73.6	69.3
Compressive Proportion									
Limit Strain	0/0	0.39	0.19	0.35	0.25	0.49	0.22	0.28	0.14
Compressive Failure Strain	0/0	1.40	0.95	1.35	1.00	1.06	0.50	1.10	0.50
Fibre Volume Ratio	0/0	58.6	58.6	58.0	58.0	57.0	57.0	57.4	57.4

Table 4 The compressive behaviors of the cross HFRP

		A				B			
		0° layer is G		0° layer is C		0° layer is G		0° layer is C	
		$[0_2^G/90_2^C]_s$	$[90_2^C/0_2^G]_s$	$[0_2^C/90_2^G]_s$	$[90_2^G/0_2^C]_s$	$[0_2^G/90_2^C]_s$	$[90_2^G/0_2^G]_s$	$[0_2^C/90_2^G]_s$	$[90_2^G/0_2^C]_s$
Compressive Strength	Mpa	249	112	416	204	282	119	479	209
Compressive Modulus	Gpa	32.5	35.6	70.6	71.0	34.7	34.2	71.0	65.6
Compressive Proportion									
Limit Strain	0/0	0.38	0.20	0.40	0.16	0.55	0.20	0.55	0.16
Compressive Failure Strain	0/0	1.40	0.55	0.90	0.97	1.40	0.55	1.07	0.97
Fibre Volume Ratio	0/0	60	58	58	60	59	63	63	59

2. After the matrix is toughened, the transverse tensile strength and elongation of the unidirectional composites will increase sharply. But transverse compressive strength and modulus decrease slightly.
3. When the matrix toughness is increased, the tensile strength of the crossplied laminates increases and that of outside 0° composites are larger than outside 90° ones.
4. In the toughened matrix crossplied laminates, when the 90° layers are replaced with hybrid ones, the tensile strength and elongation will increase.
5. The matrix toughness decrease the compressive properties of mono-fibre cross plied laminates with outside 0° layers, but, it can increase the compressive strength of them with outside 90° layers.
6. The matrix toughness can increase the compressive behaviors of the cross-plyed HFRP. Aside from ones with outside 90° layers, their modulus decrease.

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Fig.3 Tensile stress-strain curves of the crossplied composites

4. Polymer Matrices

